

Antioxidant Property and Cytotoxicity of *Crescentia cujete* L. (Calabash) Using Hydrogen Peroxide Scavenging and Brine Shrimp Lethality Assays

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Abstract

Breast cancer remains one of the leading causes of mortality among women worldwide, largely due to its complexity, progression, and ability to develop resistance to conventional therapies. This has led to increasing interest in plant-derived compounds as potential sources of alternative therapeutic agents. *Crescentia cujete* L. (Calabash), a plant widely used in traditional medicine for conditions such as hypertension, respiratory diseases, and infections, is believed to contain bioactive compounds with possible pharmacological effects. However, studies investigating its antioxidant and cytotoxic properties remain limited. This study aimed to evaluate the antioxidant activity and cytotoxic potential of *C. cujete* fruit extract using the hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay and brine shrimp lethality assay. The antioxidant activity was assessed based on the ability of the extract to scavenge hydrogen peroxide at varying concentrations, while cytotoxicity was determined by exposing *A. salina* nauplii to different extract concentrations and calculating mortality rates to estimate the LC₅₀ using probit analysis. Results revealed that the extract exhibited a dose-dependent antioxidant activity, with increased hydrogen peroxide scavenging observed at higher concentrations. Similarly, the extract demonstrated significant cytotoxic effects against *A. salina*, with higher concentrations resulting in increased mortality. The computed LC₅₀ value indicates that the extract possesses notable bioactivity. Overall, the findings suggest that *C. cujete* L. fruit extract contains compounds with antioxidant and cytotoxic properties, supporting its potential as a candidate for further pharmacological and anticancer research.

Keywords: Antioxidant property, *Artemia salina* (Brine shrimp), Breast cancer, *Crescentia cujete* L. (Calabash), Cytotoxicity

Introduction

Breast cancer is one of the leading causes of death among women worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (2024), it is the most prevalent cancer among women and the second most common cancer globally. In 2022, there were approximately 2.3 million new cases and 670,000 deaths attributed to the disease. Although mortality rates have declined in many Western countries due to improved screening and treatment, breast cancer remains a growing concern in several parts of Asia. In countries such as China, it continues to be a leading cause of cancer-related deaths among women, particularly those aged 15–44 (Hong et al., 2022). These trends highlight the need for continued research on

accessible and alternative approaches to cancer prevention and treatment. In the Philippines, breast cancer is the third leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women. It is estimated that one in 13 Filipino women may develop breast cancer in their lifetime, with incidence increasing with age (Yap et al., 2023). Despite its high prevalence, there is limited local research exploring natural food sources with potential anticancer properties. Investigating plant-based alternatives may provide cost-effective and accessible options for disease management and prevention.

Crescentia cujete L. (Calabash) is a plant known for its traditional medicinal uses in various cultures. According to Balogun et al. (2021), different parts of the plant have been used to treat conditions such as hypertension, respiratory diseases, and internal infections. These applications suggest that the plant may contain bioactive compounds with potential therapeutic value. However, studies focusing on its antioxidant activity and cytotoxic effects, particularly in relation to cancer models, remain limited. Given this gap, the present study aimed to evaluate the antioxidant properties and cytotoxic potential of *Crescentia cujete* L. using *Artemia salina* (Brine shrimp) as a model organism. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the percentage scavenging activity and IC₅₀ of *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) extract at different concentrations using the H₂O₂ scavenging assay?
2. Does *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) exhibit cytotoxic effects against *A. salina* (brine shrimp) nauplii?
3. What is the mortality rate of *A. salina* nauplii and the LC₅₀ of *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) extract?
4. Is there a significant difference in the percentage scavenging activity of *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) extract at different concentrations?

Methodology

Preparation of Plant Materials and Extract

Mature *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) fruits from identified healthy trees were collected together with their GPS or location, date, and tree ID. The fruits were washed, and the unwanted parts were removed. The *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) fruits were sun-dried for two hours until constant weight. The dried fruits were ground into powder and stored in an airtight container at 4 degrees Celsius. The 500 milliliter of dried *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) powder was mixed with 500 milliliter of 95% ethanol (1:1 w/v). It was macerated for 48 hours with occasional shaking and filtered using a filter paper. The filtrate was reduced using a rotary evaporator. The crude extract was dissolved in analytical grade methanol to make a stock of 10 mg/mL. It was filtered and stored at 4 degree Celsius in an Erlenmeyer flask. In the preparation of different treatments, 5 concentrations (10 µg/mL, 25 µg/mL, 50 µg/mL, 100 µg/mL, and 200 µg/mL) were used.

Hydrogen Peroxide Scavenging Assay

The hydrogen peroxide solution was prepared by diluting 0.1 mL H₂O₂ into 9.9 mL of distilled water, for a total of 10 mL. The diluted solution was diluted again by taking 0.1 mL of the diluted solution and mixing it with 9.9 mL of distilled water. The phosphate buffer solution was prepared by measuring 15 mL into a separate graduated cylinder. The

antioxidant solution contains 15 test tubes, and in each test tube, 1 mL of phosphate buffer was mixed with other solutions. A crude extract stock solution of 10 mg/mL was prepared and serially diluted with distilled water to obtain working concentrations of 50, 100, and 200 µg/mL. The ascorbic acid was prepared by weighing 10 µg and diluting it with distilled water. This solution served as the positive control for the antioxidant property, and at the same concentrations, while distilled water served as the negative control. For the assay, equal volumes of hydrogen peroxide solution, phosphate buffer, and plant extract at desired concentrations, or ascorbic acid and distilled water are mixed in test tubes. The mixtures were stored at the open room temperature for 10 minutes. The percentage radical scavenging activity (%RSA) was calculated using the formula:

$$\%RSA = \left[\frac{\text{Absorbance control} - \text{Absorbance sample}}{\text{Absorbance control}} \times 100 \right]$$

All treatments were performed in triplicate, and the mean and standard deviation were computed. The %RSA values were plotted against the logarithm of concentration to estimate the IC₅₀ value using regression analysis.

Brine Shrimp Lethality (BLS) Assay

A. salina cysts were hatched in artificial seawater prepared by dissolving 35 g/L of sea salt in distilled water, achieving a salinity of approximately 25 – 35 ppt and a pH of about 8.0. The setup was maintained under continuous aeration and constant illumination at 26–28 °C for 24–48 hours. Free-swimming stage I–II nauplii (≤48 hours old) were then collected, rinsed with fresh artificial seawater, and transferred into test tubes. Plant extracts were prepared at concentrations of 10, 25, 50, 100, and 200 µg/mL. Diluted hydrogen peroxide in the potassium buffer served as the negative control, while ascorbic acid (≤1% v/v in artificial seawater) and potassium dichromate were used as positive controls. For each treatment, 10 mL of the test solution containing nauplii was placed into vials, with three replicates per concentration. The test tubes were placed inside a 1 L beaker and kept at room temperature without feeding. After 24 hours, the number of live and dead nauplii was counted. Mortality was calculated across replicates, and LC₅₀ values with 95% confidence intervals were estimated using probit analysis.

Statistical Analysis

In analyzing the data collected from the study, the area, mean, and standard deviation were calculated for each treatment and control group. Before inferential testing, the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were evaluated using the Shapiro–Wilk test and Levene’s test, respectively. For the hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay, the percentage radical scavenging activity (%RSA) at each concentration was plotted against the logarithm of the concentration to generate a dose–response curve. The IC₅₀ value was then estimated using nonlinear regression analysis. Differences in %RSA among the different concentrations were analyzed using One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), followed by post hoc comparisons using the Least Significant Difference (LSD)

test. For the brine shrimp lethality assay, mortality counts and proportions were recorded per vial, and the mean mortality percentage was calculated for each concentration. Mortality data were analyzed using probit regression with log-transformed concentrations to estimate the LC₅₀ value at a 95% confidence level.

Ethical Considerations

This study did not involve human participants or higher vertebrate animals. *C. Cujete L.* (Calabash) and *A. salina* (brine shrimp) were used as test organisms, both of which posed minimal ethical concerns. The fruits of *C. kujete L.* (Calabash) were collected responsibly without causing harm to the tree population, and proper identification and documentation of the plant material were carried out. The brine shrimp lethality assay was conducted in accordance with ethical laboratory practices, ensuring that only the minimum number of nauplii necessary to obtain valid results was used. All test organisms were properly disposed of after experimentation. Standard laboratory safety protocols were strictly followed, including the proper handling, storage, and disposal of solvents and reagents. Overall, the study complied with established biosafety guidelines and ethical standards for research involving non-vertebrate organisms and natural products.

Results and Discussion

Number of Deaths and Mortality Rate of *A. salina* nauplii in Brine Shrimp Lethality (BLS) Assay After Exposure

Quantifying the mortality of *A. salina* nauplii provides a basis for evaluating the toxicity of *C. kujete L.* (calabash). Table 1 summarizes the number of deaths and corresponding mortality rates observed in the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BLSA)

Table 1. Mortality Rate of *A. salina* nauplii in Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BLSA)

Treatment	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Total	Mean	%Mortality	Corrected %Mortality
T ₁ DH ₂ O	0	0	2	2	0.67	6.67	0.00
T ₂ K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	10	10	10	30	10.00	100.00	100.00
T ₃ (10 µg/mL)	4	5	3	12	4.00	40.00	35.71
T ₄ (25 µg/mL)	10	10	10	30	10.00	100.00	100.00
T ₅ (50 µg/mL)	9	10	9	28	9.33	93.33	92.86
T ₆ (100 µg/mL)	10	10	10	30	10.00	100.00	100.00
T ₇ (200 µg/mL)	10	10	10	30	10.00	100.00	100.00

Table 1 shows that the corrected mortality of *A. salina* nauplii varied across treatments after exposure, indicating differences in cytotoxic activity following adjustment using Abbott's formula. Treatments T₂, T₄, T₆, and T₇ exhibited the highest corrected mortality at 100.00%, indicating complete lethality and the strongest cytotoxic effects among all treatments. In contrast, T₁ showed the lowest corrected mortality at 0.00%, suggesting a negligible toxic effect after accounting for natural mortality. Furthermore, T₃ exhibited a corrected mortality of 35.71%, indicating weak cytotoxic activity, whereas T₅ showed a markedly higher corrected mortality of 92.86%, reflecting strong cytotoxic activity but not complete

lethality. Overall, an increasing trend in corrected mortality was observed from T₃ to T₇, suggesting a dose-dependent increase in cytotoxicity.

The reliability of the results is supported by the consistency of outcomes across the three replicates. Moreover, the corrected mortality values confirm that the observed lethality is attributable to the concentration of the treatment rather than background mortality. This finding is consistent with the study of Billacura and Laciapag (2017), which reported that the fruit of *C. cujete* L. (calabash) exhibits significant cytotoxicity and bioactivity as demonstrated by brine shrimp lethality assays. Their study concluded that the fruit is a potent source of bioactive compounds with toxic properties.

Determining the LC₅₀ Using the Probit Regression Analysis

In determining the toxicity of *C. cujete* L. (Calabash), Probit Regression Analysis was used to demonstrate the varying amounts of the chemical affect mortality. Table 2 presents the LC₅₀ of *A. salina* nauplii in the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BLSA).

Table 2. LC₅₀ of *A. salina* nauplii in Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BLSA)

LC ₅₀	Chi-square	p-value	Interpretation
12.412	12.024	0.007	Highly Toxic

Table 2 showed that the LC₅₀ value of *A. salina* nauplii after an hour of exposure was 12.412 µg/mL. The chi-square result ($\chi^2 = 12.024$, $p = 0.007$) showed that the data fit the model well and was also statistically significant. Based on the LC₅₀ value, the test sample was classified as highly toxic, showing strong toxic effects on the brine shrimp within an hour of exposure. This result is consistent with research by Balogun and Sabiu (2021), who found that all *C. cujete* L. fruit extracts are poisonous and bioactive to the cells because Meyer's toxicity index LC₅₀ values were less than 1000 ppm.

Figure 1. Probit Dose-Response Curve

Figure 1 shows that the test sample showed noticeable toxicity. The probit dose-response curve clearly demonstrates a positive correlation between log concentration and mortality in *A. salina* nauplii, suggesting that more harmful effects were produced at higher concentrations. The high coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.5749$) and fitted regression line ($y = 1.428x + 3.7834$). A consistent dose-response pattern was confirmed by the increasing trend of probit values across concentrations. The results indicated that the cytotoxicity of *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) differs depending on how high the concentration of the extract was employed, as it was a concentration-dependent extract. This result aligns with the findings of Januario et al.(2022) that the extract revealed an LC_{50} value comparable to $28.75 \mu\text{g/mL}$, exhibiting a significant degree of cytotoxicity/bioactivity. It implied that plant extract with more than the LC_{50} value corresponds to $12.412 \mu\text{g/mL}$; the concentration of the extract is highly toxic to nauplii. However, more investigation is needed for confirmation. The results support the pattern, indicating that the appropriate amount of dosage of *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) extract is essential for determining its mortality.

Mean Gray Value (MGV) of Hydrogen Peroxide Scavenging Assay

Determining the Mean Gray Value (MGV) of *C. cujete* L. (calabash) provides a quantitative basis for evaluating its antioxidant activity. Table 3 presents the MGV values of *C. cujete* L. across the different treatment concentrations.

Table 3. Mean Gray Value (MGV) of Hydrogen Peroxide Scavenging Assay

Treatment	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Mean	%Inhibition
T ₁ - DH ₂ O	101.6	102.4	106.9	103.63	---
T ₂ - C ₆ H ₈ O ₆	105.2	139.5	115.1	119.93	-15.12
T ₃ - 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	37.00	23.70	35.70	32.13	69.01
T ₄ - 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	25.40	31.10	21.10	25.87	75.03
T ₅ - 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	22.50	27.00	45.30	31.60	75.78

Table 3 presents the Mean Gray Value (MGV) and percentage inhibition of the different treatments in the hydrogen scavenging assay. T₁, which served as the control, recorded a mean MGV of 103.63 and showed no inhibitory activity. Similarly, T₂ exhibited a higher mean MGV (119.93) than the control, resulting in a negative inhibition value (-15.12%), indicating the absence of hydrogen scavenging activity and suggesting a possible pro-oxidant effect. In contrast, T₃, T₄, and T₅ demonstrated markedly lower mean MGV values (32.13, 25.87, and 31.60, respectively), corresponding to high inhibition percentages of 69.01%, 75.03%, and 75.78%.

These findings imply that the extracted bioactive ingredients are efficient at lowering hydrogen peroxide and preventing the production of more dangerous reactive oxygen species and indicate a strong hydrogen radical scavenging activity, reflecting substantial antioxidant potential. According to Nowak (2022), this study finds phenolic antioxidants act as such at lower/moderate concentrations by scavenging radicals, but at higher levels generate reactive intermediates with pro-oxidant effects. Higher concentrations do not always boost antioxidant activity and may be harmful.

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between concentration and percentage inhibition, showing that inhibition increases rapidly at low concentrations and continues to rise gradually until reaching a maximum of nearly 90% at around 130 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ to 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. There is a slight decline in inhibition observed, suggesting a reduced effectiveness at higher doses of *C. kujete* L. (Calabash). The quadratic model ($y = -0.0045x^2 + 1.2509x + 4.8458$) provides a strong fit to the data, as indicated by the high R^2 value of 0.9292, confirming the reliability of the trend in the figure.

Figure 2. IC_{50} of *C. kujete* L. (Calabash) extract at different concentrations

Based on the curve, approximately 50% inhibition occurs at around 30 to 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, indicating moderate inhibitory potency of the test sample. Overall, it demonstrates a clear dose-dependent inhibitory response with an optimal concentration range for maximum activity. The results aligned with the study of Limanan et al. (2025), in which *C. kujete* L. (Calabash) extract demonstrated moderate antioxidant capacity ($\text{IC}_{50} = 158.45 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$).

Determining the Significant Difference in the Percentage Scavenging Activity of *C. Cujete* L. (Calabash) Extract at Different Concentrations

Determining the significant differences in the percentage scavenging activity of *C. kujete* L. (Calabash) extract across varying concentrations provides a basis for evaluating its antioxidant effectiveness. Tables 4, 5, and 6 present the normality testing using the Shapiro-Wilk test, One-Way Analysis of Variance Across Treatments, and the Least Significant Difference (LSD) Test of the MGV across the different treatments.

Table 4. Test for Normality Using the Shapiro-Wilk Test

Treatment	Statistics	df	Sig.	Interpretation
T ₁	0.860	3	0.268	Normal
T ₂	0.944	3	0.543	Normal
T ₃	0.823	3	0.170	Normal
T ₄	0.994	3	0.846	Normal
T ₅	0.932	3	0.497	Normal

Table 4 showed that all treatments obtained significance values that were found in the Shapiro-Wilk test, which ranged between 0.170 and 0.846, and were greater than 0.01, which implies that there was no deviation from a normal distribution.

Table 5. Summary of One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Across Treatments

	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Between Groups	25939.89	4	6484.97	80.23	0.00	Reject Ho
Within Groups	808.33	10	80.83			
Total	26748.22	14				

Table 5 revealed that the variance within the groups to the variance between the treatment groups is represented by the F-value of 80.23. The observed changes between the treatments are statistically significant and hereby reject the null hypotheses (H_0), as indicated by the significance value of 0.00, which was less than the 0.01 level of significance. This indicates that there was a significant difference between at least one treatment group and the other. This outcome demonstrates that the effects of the various *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) extract concentrations varied noticeably.

Table 6. Least Significant Difference (LSD) Test

(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Sig.	Interpretation
1	2	0.051	Not Significant
	3	0.000	Significant
	4	0.000	Significant
	5	0.000	Significant
2	3	0.000	Significant
	4	0.000	Significant
	5	0.000	Significant
3	4	0.413	Not Significant
	5	0.361	Not Significant
4	5	0.919	Not Significant

Table 6 revealed that the post hoc test results revealed that there was a highly significant difference between T_1 and T_3 , T_4 , and T_5 ($p = 0.000$), which means that these treatments have significantly higher values compared to T_1 . Moreover, there was no significant difference between T_1 and T_2 ($p = 0.051$), as the value was greater than the 0.01 level of significance. Similarly, T_2 did not exhibit a significant change from T_1 ($p = 0.051$), but it did exhibit a highly significant difference from T_3 , T_4 , and T_5 ($p = 0.000$). Conversely, because the values (0.413, 0.361, and 0.919) were higher than the level of significance, T_3 , T_4 , and T_5 did not exhibit any significant differences from one another. Based on the results, T_3 , T_4 , and T_5 have almost the same effects, while T_1 and T_2 significantly differ compared to T_3 , T_4 , and T_5 . This implies that the higher-level treatments significantly produced different results compared to the lower-level treatments, which shows the effectiveness of the increased level of treatment.

Similar to the findings of the research done by Billacura and Laciapag (2017), the bioactivity of the fruit of *C. cujete* L. was found to be cytotoxic, and it may have components with anthelmintic as well as antioxidant activities. Also, the results aligned with the study of Gonzales et al. (2023), whereas the previous study showed that the fruit and leaves of *C. cujete* L. (Calabash) have significant levels of flavonoids and phenolic substances, which scavenge free radicals and give them remarkable antioxidant qualities.

Conclusions

The present study demonstrates that *C. cujete* L. (calabash) fruit extract possesses significant antioxidant and cytotoxic properties, supporting its potential as a source of bioactive compounds. The extract exhibited notable hydrogen peroxide-scavenging activity, with an IC₅₀ of 30-40 µg/mL, indicating moderate to strong antioxidant capacity. In addition, the extract showed a clear dose-dependent cytotoxic effect on *A. salina* nauplii, with higher concentrations resulting in higher mortality. The computed LC₅₀ values of 12.412 µg/mL further confirm its high toxicity. Statistical analysis also revealed a significant difference in scavenging activity across concentrations, reinforcing the concentration-dependent efficacy of the extract. Overall, these findings suggest that *C. cujete* L. contains biologically active constituents that may be valuable in antioxidant applications and preliminary toxicity screening, providing a scientific basis for its potential use in future pharmacological and therapeutic studies.

Contributions of Authors

The authors indicate equal contributions to each section. The authors reviewed and approved the final work.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding this paper.

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